

**FIRST AFFILIATED HOSPITAL of GUANGXI MEDICAL
UNIVERSITY**

ETHICAL REVIEW COMMITTEE Approval Notice

Approval Number: 2024-E685-01

Title: Development and Multicenter Validation of a Machine Learning Based Preoperative Prediction Model for Postoperative Delirium in Cervical Spondylotic Myelopathy: A Real-World Study

Research Contents: Abstract

Background: Cervical spondylotic myelopathy (CSM) is recognized as one of the most severe forms of degenerative cervical spine disease and frequently requires surgical intervention. Postoperative delirium is a common complication in this population and can substantially affect postoperative recovery and long-term outcomes. This study aimed to develop and validate a machine learning based preoperative prediction model for postoperative delirium in patients with CSM.

Methods: Data were collected from 789 patients across three clinical centers, comprising a retrospective cohort of 640 patients and a prospective cohort of 149 patients. Key clinical and laboratory predictors were selected using Lasso regression. Multiple machine learning algorithms were then applied to develop predictive models. Model performance was evaluated and compared using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves, area under the curve (AUC), calibration analysis, and decision curve analysis (DCA). To enhance interpretability, SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) were used to elucidate feature contributions. Finally, the optimal model was deployed as an online tool using a Shiny-based web application.

Results: The final model incorporated eleven key predictors. Among the ten machine learning algorithms evaluated, the SVM model achieved the best predictive performance, with an AUC of 0.84 in the internal test cohort and 0.83 in the external validation cohort. Additionally, age, MONO, and ESRemerged as the most influential predictors.

Conclusions: This predictive tool provides a robust foundation for individualized postoperative management in CSM patients and holds promise for reducing the risk of postoperative delirium.

Applicant: 刘冲

Application Department: Department of Spine and Osteopathy Ward

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Conclusion: This paper fully considered and protected the rights and interests of the study objects. It meets the criteria of Ethical Review Committee. The Medical Ethics Committee of First Affiliated Hospital of Guangxi Medical University has approved the protocol.

Signature:

(Vice) Director of Ethical Review Committee

First Affiliated Hospital of Guangxi Medical University

Date: September 24, 2024

